

Report

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Migration and demographic patterns in Central-Eastern Europe

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Abstract

This report is a part of deliverable "D.6.2. Report on migration and demographic patterns in the EU CEE countries and potential source countries" from the project FUME – Future Migration Scenarios for Europe (870649), financed with the Horizon 2020 programme. In particular, this country report focuses on critical analysis of migration data from Romania, and in particular - immigration data. The analysis consists of an overview of stock and flow data on migrants including such dimensions as age groups, gender, country of origin and length of residence. This report is a first step in analytical exercise which aims to determine migration potential from and to Romania and furthermore, to provide necessary data input for fine-tuning of FUME migration projection model.

Romania has been among the largest emigration countries in southeastern Europe for the last couple of decades. Socio-economic and political transformation brought many challenges and led to a number of waves of Romanian emigrants who settled mainly in Western and Southern Europe, but also in the United States and Canada. Recent migration patterns were largely determined by the process of European integration which brought new mobility and work opportunities. According to recent official statistics, the number of emigrants since 2011 has been higher than immigrants, and is relatively stable. On the other hand, immigration to Romania is still not significant, although it is on the increase in the last couple of years. Among new trends in immigrations is the arrival of Asian workers, mainly from China or Vietnam, which is a response to a lack of workforce in Romania.

This report presents the historical framework of migration transformation, diaspora dynamics and major national groups of immigrants and their demographic structure. It also provides critical analysis of the validity of the main statistical data sources, and draws some conclusions on migration patterns and trends in Romania.

1. Introduction

In the last couple of decades, Romania used to be characterized as an emigration country. In the European Union, it is among the top sending countries with negative net migration, followed by Poland, Albania and Lithuania (United Nations, 2019: 24). Romanian international migration became significant after the fall of the Iron Curtain in 1989 and the of tight control over population movements¹. Since then, in the context of major economic and political transformations, the country witnessed many waves of emigrants heading mostly towards Western and Southern European countries, involving even 3,5 millions of Romanian citizens who temporarily or permanently changed their place of residence (United Nations, 2017).

Following the decline of state socialism, three distinct phases in migration processes and patterns can be distinguished: 1) liberalized, although still restricted migration in the 1990s, 2) an increase in irregular migration in the period of 2002 – 2007, 3) an unrestricted movement inside the EU since Romania's accession in 2007 (Anghel et al., 2016).

The 1990s were marked by the liberalization of migration control and restrictions which resulted in an increase of external migration. Although the state no longer prohibited Romanian citizens from going abroad, emigration was limited by other European countries which required a visa or a work permit from foreigners. At first, mass emigration of ethnic German population residing formerly in Romania took place. They either used their family connections to apply for a visa or took advantage of the opportunities resulting from a tourist visa (Ciobanu 2010). Another significant group of emigrants consisted of those who were granted refugee status in Western Europe, among others in France and Germany (Ciobanu 2015). Other top countries for emigrants were Hungary and Israel, whereas in the late 1990s also overseas destinations, mainly the United States and Canada (OECD 2019). International mobility in that period included small-scale trade between Romania and countries such as former Yugoslavia, Turkey, Poland, and Hungary. Although people engaged in this form of trade retained Romanian residence, some of them were the pioneers of subsequent long-term emigration (Anghel et al., 2016: 9).

The year 2002 brought another shift in migration dynamics, i.e., further liberalization in transnational mobility. From that moment, Romanian citizens are allowed to enter the Schengen area without a visa or a residence permit for up to three months. Officially, this right was granted for tourists, but it opened a path for irregular migrants and people without legal documents (Ciobanu, 2015: 471-2). Many Romanians went abroad to work, and their presence in EU countries increased significantly after 2002. Moreover, Romanian authorities participated in labour recruitment, which led to bilateral agreements e.g., with Spain in 2002 (Anghel et al. 2016: 16). These emigration movements are depicted, to some extent, in European statistics. While in 2001 there were officially 0.3 million of Romanian citizens in the European Union, in 2010 their number increased to 2.1 million (Eurostat 2011).

¹ Notable exception was the emigration of Germans and Jews, which was supported by the respective countries (Tompea, Nastuta 2009: 218).

In 2007 new features in Romanian migration regimes appeared as the country became the European Union's member, and got access to many, albeit not all, European labour markets². Romanian citizens were granted many social and political rights. However, the economic crisis in 2008 led to a change in destination countries for Romanians, for instance from southern to northern Europe (such as the UK and Germany). Seasonal and temporary migration is still observed, as well as return migration (Anghel et al., 2016: 17).

Concerning immigration processes, even though the inflows of migrants have been increasing in Romania, especially in recent years, the overall percentage of foreigners remains low. Except for the "traditional" and persistent immigration of citizens of the Republic of Moldova for whom the process might be easier due to cultural and linguistic proximity³, there has been an intensified migration from other countries, too. Other numerous groups of migrants originate from Italy and Spain and other EU member states which are also main emigration countries for Romanians. Hence, some part of them might be Romanian returnees, but there is no official data available that would depict return migration. It is, therefore, impossible to precisely assess the inflow of foreigners arriving in Romania.

Other non-EU member states that are countries of origin of immigrants coming to Romania are Ukraine, Turkey and China. Also, intensified immigrant flows from Asian countries such as Vietnam, Nepal, India and Sri Lanka have been observed in recent years. It is a relatively new and an ongoing phenomenon that seems to be reshaping the migration landscape in Romania.

Acknowledgments

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² The countries which immediately – in 2007 - allowed access to their labour markets for Romanian migrants – were the countries which joined the EU in 2004 (except from Malta and Hungary) together with Sweden and Finland. Then, in 2009, Denmark, Greece, Hungary and Portugal lifted their restrictions, whereas in 2012 Ireland and Italy. The final liberalization and the granting of full rights on the European labour markets took place in 2013 with the end of a transition period (cf. Dąbrowski, 2014).

³ After the First World War, the so-called Greater Romanian encompassed lands which had been annexed to Romania, i.e., Bessarabia, Transylvania, the Banat and Bukovina. Consequently, Romanian identity and culture was promoted among various ethnic groups.

Picture: Bogdan Cotos/Unsplash.com

2. Methodology, Definitions and Sources

Methodological approach

This report was based upon a desk research method and critical data analysis. The first step was to gather the main relevant data on immigration numbers (stock and flows) from official sources in Romania and other Central and Eastern European countries belonging to the EU. Data were obtained mainly from the Romanian National Statistical Institute and Eurostat, as well as reports on recent migration processes related to the analysed country. Relevant academic literature and policy papers have also been consulted. The main theme of interest was immigration, but an overview of emigration and a discussion of the diaspora is also included. The research team has therefore paid special attention to existing and available data on immigrant stocks and flows. The report provides a critical assessment of those data suggesting biases and problems in data collection and reliability. The migration statistics provided by the official Romanian sources was finally compared with the estimations on immigrant flows by Abel & Cohen (2019).

Evidencing of migrants in statistical registers and definitions of migrants

Whereas the statistics for external migration from Romania are available since the communist era, official data on immigrants have only been gathered since the 1990s. Up to 2006, the available statistics on migration flows to and from Romania only indicated the numbers of people who settled permanently either in Romania or another country. That procedure led to a large underestimation of real migration. Likewise, the stocks of immigrants in Romania in the 2002 census also were miscalculated and did not include all groups of foreign-born (Tompea and Nastuta, 2009: 2018).

There are several institutions that provide data on migration in contemporary Romania that can be used to assess the scale of migration and migrants' characteristics. Official migration statistical information is gathered by the National Institute of Statistics (NIS). The data the NIS presents in Statistical Yearbooks and on their website come from two categories of sources:

- 1) **exhaustive** (population or housing censuses which cover the stocks of the population; the most recent were conducted in 1992, 2002 and 2011) or **sample statistical surveys**, which result from the Yearly National Statistical Programme (YNSP). The most recent census was conducted in 2011 (The Population and Housing Census);
- 2) **administrative sources** (NIS 2018: VII-VIII).

Data from censuses are, however, not always comparable. For example, censuses in 1992 and 2002 applied different definitions of populations, which had practical implications for the measurement process. The latter determined the Romanian population in relation to the 1998 UN recommendation for defining international migration. In practical terms, while in 1992 all people with legal residence status in Romania were counted as a part of the Romanian population, even those who had left the country, and lived abroad. On the other hand, the 2002 census did not count those Romanian citizens who had left the country and remained abroad for at least one year, even in cases when they still had permanent residence in Romania. Another difference between those two censuses was related to the estimations of foreign citizens. While in 1992 out of all foreigners in Romania only those who were "permanent" migrants were counted (i.e., those who had officially registered

their new address and got permanent residency right), in 2002 - for the first time - all foreign citizens who had been residing on the Romanian territory for at least one year were taken into account (Tompea and Nastuta, 2009; 2019-2020).

Recent statistical yearbooks provided by the National Institute of Statistics contain the following international migration stocks-related information: number of emigrants by age and sex group as well as country of destination; number of immigrants by age and sex group with information on a country of previous residence (NIS, 2018: 36). Currently the NIS website enables access to statistical yearbooks for the period of 2006 – 2019. In the latest (as of January 2021), publicly available yearbook from 2019, statistics for 2018 are only provisional (NIS, Statistical Yearbooks of Romania 2020c).

Additional migration data are being gathered by the following institutions, which, since 2006, have been obliged to report to the NIS (Tompea and Nastuta, 2009; NIS, 2018):

- General Inspectorate for Immigration (IGI), within the Ministry of Internal Affairs, holds a database on registered foreigners who have permanent residence in Romania. It provides data on third-country nationals living in Romania, as well as information on the asylum seekers and refugees.
- National Authority for Citizenship which can provide information on the number of applications for Romanian citizenship.
- the General Inspectorate of the Border Police, which monitors the movement across the borders and collects information on the number of people not allowed to enter or leave Romania.
- the National Office for Refugees, which has data on the number of asylum seekers in Romania.
- Ministry of Home Affairs: Directorate for Personal Records and Database Administration (DEPABD).
- Passports General Directorate.

Nevertheless, a lot of migration-related data is not publicly available neither at the NIS nor particular institutions' websites. Before discussing the statistics relevant to emigration and immigration, the terms used by the Romanian statistical institutions will be shortly presented.

International migration

The term "international migration" in Romania is operationalized in relation to the type of residence in another state (permanent or usual residence), the period of residence (short or long-term), and citizenship. Permanent migration refers to those persons who have changed their permanent residence to or from Romania and established a legal residence. This fact should be formalized by a declaration of the address where a migrant lives and official registration.

Long-term migration refers to a change in one's residence for a period of at least one year. Short term, on the other hand, is used to refer to a change in residence that lasts less than 12 months. It is important to note that Romanian statistics do not count short term migrants (Roman 2019).

Emigration

The definitions of emigrants and immigrants in Romanian statistical registers are determined in accordance with European regulations and use the residence criteria. Consequently, the term “emigrant” refers to a person from Romania who changed their usual residence in other countries. To be officially considered an emigrant one should de-register from his/her previous residence and move abroad for at least 12 months. Emigrants flow data represent, thus, the number of migrants who left Romania and settled abroad for at least a year (NIS, 2018: 41-2). There is, however, no official data on the number of return migrants, so the trend of Romanian citizens coming back to their former homeland is difficult to assess (Anghel and Coşciug, 2018).

Immigration

Immigration is defined by Romanian authorities as an action of coming to their country from abroad and settling on the territory of Romania for at least one year. Immigrant flow refers to both Romanian citizens (“return migrants”) and foreigners who had previously lived abroad (NIS, 2018: 41). This category covers immigrants coming from and outside the EU.

The concept of immigrants used in statistical documents refers to: “Romanian citizens, foreigners or without citizenship who settled their usual residence in Romania” (NIS, 2018: 39). There are two categories used in this context: “permanent” and “temporary” immigration. Temporary immigrants include “foreign citizens or stateless who had previously been usually resident in another country and established their usual residence in Romania for at least 12 months”, as well as “Romanian citizens who had previously been usually resident abroad for at least 12 months and returned in Romania for a period of at least 12 months”, while permanent immigrants are those who have declared their address in Romania as their main dwelling. The act of declaration is confirmed in official documents, such as an identity card (NIS, 2020a).

In this context, the term “usual residence” is defined as: “the place at which a person normally spends the daily period of rest, regardless of temporary absences for purposes of recreation, holiday, visits to friends and relatives, business, medical treatment or religious pilgrimage” (Ibidem).

Short and long-term migrants

A short-term migrant is defined as a person who has changed his/her place of residence for at least three months, but less than a year, while a long-term migrant - for at least 12 months (NIS, 2020b).

Migration flows

International migration flows mean changing the usual residence from and to Romania for at least 12 months. Until 2002 these processes were assessed on the basis of only administrative sources taking into account the change of permanent residence. Since 2002 additional sources and methodology have also been used in Romania. They included the econometric model based on estimation techniques, annual migration flow series (both immigrants and emigrants) obtained from Italian and Spanish statistical offices, Eurostat statistics, according to the migration data provided for Romania by other countries (“mirror” statistics) (NIS, 2018: 41-42).

According to experts, the official statistics – both the flow and stocks – do not represent the real scale of international migration from and to Romania. Since the beginning of the liberalization of migration regimes in this country in the early 1990s, there have been many shifts in migration patterns, many of which are not accounted for. In particular, temporary and circular forms of migration became a common phenomenon since the Schengen Area lifted its visa restrictions for people from Romania. Migration without legalisation has also been on the rise, and no official statistics register that trend (Tompea and Nastuta, 2009; Ciobanu, 2010).

The data provided by the NIS on the basis of available administrative sources do not cover the entire international mobility. Moreover, collecting data on permanent migration is mainly based on self-reporting, which is a condition many migrants do not fulfil. Consequently, there is a significant underestimation of the external migration processes (Otoiu and Titan, 2015).

In regard to official stocks statistics, there are also biases, and many people (i.e., temporary, or those without valid residence permits) are not counted by the existing methodological approach. Nevertheless, residence and work permits registers constitute an important source of information and should be included in the analysis of immigration processes (Tompea and Nastuta, 2009).

Residence Permits and Registrations for EU Nationals

The Emergency Ordinance no 194/2002 is the main legal framework which regulates the stay of foreigners on the territory of Romania. Immigration legislation process depends on many factors, the most important being citizenship (different rules are valid for EU/EEA or people from the Swiss Confederation and for third-country nationals), purpose of stay in Romania, and duration of stay (short or long-term stay). In the case of the EU citizens, the Romanian legislation follows European provisions, and those migrants can enter the country on the basis of the EU right to free movement. For a stay which lasts longer than 3 months, EU citizens are required to register and obtain either a registration certificate or a residence card (General Inspectorate for Immigration, 2021b).

Similarly, third country nationals who wish to come and stay in Romania for more than 90 days must obtain a residence permit from the General Inspectorate for Immigration, an office within the Romanian Ministry of Internal Affairs. The type of a permit depends on the purpose of the stay (e.g., employment, study, family reunifications, business activities, etc.). Temporary residence permits are valid for 1 to 5. The other type is a long-term residence permit which can be issued to foreigners who have a history of 5-year legal stay in Romania and fulfil additional conditions. For family members of Romanian citizens this permit is valid for 10 years, whereas in other cases – for 5 years (Ibidem).

In special circumstances, Romanian authorities can grant tolerated stay to a person who does not have a valid stay right. It can be issued for a period of 6 months but can be extended if necessary (Ibidem).

Picture: Krisztian Matyas/Unsplash.com

3. Romanian diaspora

Statistics on the scale of emigration from Romania are imprecise, often provided in an aggregated form and selected on the basis of a particular definition of emigrant, which was presented before. Therefore, they do not constitute the basis for a comprehensive or reliable assessment. Moreover, in assessing the nature of emigration it is important to understand historical patterns, e.g., the interwar period where multi-ethnic "Great Romania" functioned, and, nowadays, some of the mobilities between the neighbouring countries are related to that links from the past.

Official data related to permanent emigration is released by Romanian's National Institute of Statistics in the statistical yearbooks. The main method in estimating the number of emigrants is to collect information from the destination countries' Statistical Institutes on the foreign-born or the foreign population. Based on those data, NIS estimates the number of Romanian emigrants for the main destination countries, including variables such as age and sex. Figure 1. presents data on emigration flows for the period of 2008-2019.

Figure 1. Emigration flows from Romania, 2008-2019.

Source: NIS (2020c).

Figure 2. Number of emigrants from Romania by destination country (2016)⁴.

Source: NIS, Statistical Yearbook (2018: 101).

According to various estimates, the overall size of the Romanian diaspora is much bigger than presented by NIS – the number can be even as high as between 3-5 million (Dospinescu and Russo, 2018). For example, the United Nations Population Division estimated the total number of Romanian emigrants to 3.58 million as of 2017 (United Nations, 2017). In 2015/16, OECD countries reported having approximately 3,6 million of people born in Romania. The World Bank experts give a higher number of above 4 million. Their calculation is based upon Eurostat and national census data of the main non-European destination countries for Romanians, i.e., United States, Canada, Israel and Ukraine (Dospinescu and Russo, 2018: 7). There has also been an increase in the share of Romanians who lived outside Romania in another EU country, as in 2009 the percentage was only slightly above 10% (Eurostat, 2020c).

⁴ At the moment of writing the report the most recent statistical yearbook for Romania was from 2018.

Comparison of the emigration data of the Romanian NIS and data on Romanian residents in some of the European countries presented by Eurostat show discrepancies. For example, in Spain, 370 000 of Romanian citizens were officially registered in the period of 1992 and 2005 as having arrived in the country. It's difficult to assess what percentage of them returned to Romania or moved further to other countries. Nevertheless, the 2005 Spanish stock data included 190 000 Romanians residing legally. In spite of those data, in Romanian emigration statistics for that time Spain did not constitute an important destination country. Likewise, large discrepancies were found also in the case of other European countries which attract people from Romania (Tompea and Nastuta, 2009: 224).

As it was mentioned before, there is no precise information on the return migration. Some empirical studies have shown that around 50% - 30% of Romanian households with migrant family members have returnees (Anghel et al., 2016; Anghel and Coşciug, 2018).

What is crucial in analyzing emigration processes, official data do not cover many aspects of transnational mobility, including the dynamics of temporary or seasonal migration (Andre and Roman, 2014). Apart from permanent migrants, there is a significant category of people who live outside Romania but have not definitely left their country of origin. The existing procedures for reporting one's stay are restrictive and prevent many people from registering themselves in a new place of residence. Generally, as some migration experts stress people who leave the country have fewer incentives to report their departure than arrival at a new place. Another ambiguous, although probably significant category when it comes to official statistics, encompassed those who travel abroad for a short period of time (Ciobanu 2015; Sandu 2007). Moreover, emigration which had not been legalized is not accounted for in estimating migration flows. As a result, it is clear that the data on international migration flows are incomplete and inaccurate, and the migration flows are significantly underestimated.

Picture: Jani Godari Jaes/Unsplash.com

4. Immigrant stock in Romania

Although Romania is regarded as an important emigration country, and is characterized by a negative net migration, the immigration processes have been intensifying there especially in the recent years. However, similarly to emigration processes, it is difficult to assess its real scale due to the lack of precise and consistent data. Some researchers also suggest that in many cases immigrants treat Romania as a temporary place of stay, and use it as a transit towards other European countries (cf. Jianu, 2020).

Data on the immigrant stock in Romania is very fragmented, and the National Institute for Statistics does not present it in its public database. The most recent information about the immigrant population living in Romania comes from Census 2011, and displays some of the characteristics of the immigrant group residing in this country. However, it does not describe the “immigrant population” but the persons who had their previous residence abroad or who ever resided abroad. The latter one seems to be a more precise source of information concerning the immigrant stock in Romania at the time of Census 2011. At that point of time, there were 133 368 persons residing in Romania whose country of origin was a foreign one.

Most of the persons, whose previous residence was in a foreign country, originate from the Republic of Moldova, which is linguistically and culturally linked to Romania, therefore it is easier for those immigrants to settle and integrate (Fleşer, 2012: 71). Moldovans are also the largest group of immigrants concerning the inflows of foreigners - we will focus on that process in the next section of our report.

Other numerous groups of foreigners recorded by the Census 2011 originated from Italy, Spain, Bulgaria, Hungary, Ukraine and Germany⁵. Feminization rate in most of those groups, except for the Spanish, Italian and German exceeded 50% and the share of women was the highest among the Moldovan immigrants, reaching almost 62%:

⁵ Regarding Ukraine and Bulgaria it is important to stress historical links between those countries and Romanian before the Second World War. Part of contemporary Ukraine – Bukovina – belonged to Romania in the interwar time. The same was with two territories at the Black Sea which are now inside Bulgaria’s borders – Durostor and Caliacra. When the communist system collapsed, many Romanians living in other countries took the opportunity to join to their relatives.

Table 1. Most numerous groups of persons who have ever resided abroad; by country of origin; feminization rates of immigrant groups, 2011.

Source: NIS (2011).

	Total	Female	Feminization rate
Total	133 368	65 299	49%
Republic of Moldova	28 603	17 698	61,90%
Italy	17 510	7 900	45,10%
Spain	10 158	4 705	46,30%
Bulgaria	9 309	5 589	60%
Hungary	7 214	3 773	52,30%
Ukraine	6 685	4 070	60,90%
Germany	6 040	2 652	43,90%

Data gathered during the last census in Romania provides also information about the length of residence of persons originating from abroad. As depicted by Figure 3., most of the immigrants originating from the Republic of Moldova had been residing in Romania for more than 20 years at the point of the Census 2011. Similar trend concerns the group of Bulgarian, Ukrainian and Hungarian immigrants. These are the foreigners who came to Romania at the beginning of the 1990s, when the country opened its borders and liberalized migration control. Duration of stay of most of the persons coming from Italy and Spain had been much shorter - most of them had been residing in Romania up to 10 years. Concerning German immigrants, the highest share of them had been staying in the country between 6 and 15 years:

Figure 3. Persons who have ever resided abroad by country of origin and duration of stay in Romania, 2011.

Source: NIS (2011).

Some more recent information about immigrant stocks in Romania is available in the Eurostat database. Those statistics are based on the NIS reportings but contain some additional estimations so that it is possible to evaluate the changes in the immigrant population residing in Romania in the years 2013-2019.

Figure 4. Total immigrant stock in Romania, 2013-2019; as of the 1st of January of the respective year.
Source: Eurostat (2021a).

According to the Eurostat statistics, the immigrant stock has been constantly growing in Romania and the number of foreigners increased by more than 3 times between 2013 and 2019. In the last reported year the number of immigrants amounted to 611 627 persons and constituted 3,15% of the whole population of Romania. The feminization rate decreased, however, and equalled 45,6% in 2019, meaning that the share of male immigrants in the whole foreign-born population of Romania has been increasing steadily between 2013 and 2019.

Figure 5. Most numerous immigrant groups by country of birth, 2013-2019 as of the 1st of January of the respective year.
Source: Eurostat (2021a).

Immigrant stock in Romania has been growing in recent years and, according to Eurostat data, people born in Western and Southern Europe countries settling in Romania started to contribute to that growth in a more significant way. The Republic of Moldova keeps being the main country of origin for the immigrants living in Romania, and Italy and Spain are the second and third countries of origin of the foreign population. Considering EU- born immigrants, the numbers of German, French, and British increased significantly. The most dynamic growth is observed among the UK-born population - the number of immigrants originating from that country increased by more than 10 times between 2013 and 2019. The number of German immigrants living in Romania grew 7 times and the France-born immigrant population increased by 5 times in that timespan. Ukrainian immigrant population also evolved in terms of numbers - the stock of immigrants born in that country increased by more than four times during six years between 2013 and 2019. The only immigrant population, among those most numerous ones, which decreased in that timespan, was the Bulgarian one. However, the decline in the number of Bulgarians is not very dramatic - in general, the size of that population has been quite stable in recent years.

Table 2. Most numerous immigrant groups by country of birth, 2013-2019 as of the 1st of January of the respective year.

Source: Eurostat (2021a).

	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
Bulgaria	11 163	10 866	10 465	10 882	10 640	10 543	10 272
France	3 780	4 251	6 471	9 262	12 472	15 867	18 865
Germany	3 759	4 018	6 552	10 750	15 319	20 168	26 444
Spain	18 827	22 322	29 937	35 857	41 184	47 311	53 638
Italy	22 486	25 699	38 580	46 172	53 221	62 914	69 151
Hungary	5 795	5 813	6 420	7 151	8 135	8 648	9 097
Republic of Moldova	59 670	79 741	114 654	137 406	162 223	199 703	247 326
Ukraine	8 743	9 392	11 900	14 328	17 384	24 570	37 600
United Kingdom	2 604	3 044	5 208	10 428	15 926	21 050	27 394

The age structure of the immigrant groups differs essentially. As depicted by Figure 6., foreigners living in Romania who were born in Western and Southern European countries are mostly children under the age of 15. This kind of data might indicate that most of the immigrants coming from those countries may be children of Romanian return migrants. They might have been born outside of the country of origin of their parents who might have decided to raise their children back in Romania. The only two national groups of foreigners with a prevalence of immigrants in the productive age (15-64 year old) were the Moldovans and Ukrainians. The first of them has been the largest group of immigrants since the 1990s, and the second one has been growing dynamically in the last decade.

Figure 6. Age structure of the most numerous immigrant groups, as of the 1st January of 2019.
Source: Eurostat (2021a).

The age structure of the whole immigrant population living in Romania in 2019 was as follows: persons younger than 15 year old constituted 39,8% of whole immigrant stock, the share of people in productive age, between 15 year old and 64 year old amounted to 52,8%, and persons older than 65 years constituted 7,4% of all foreigners. In general, at the beginning of 2019 there were slightly more immigrants in the productive age than in the non-productive one.

Another important source of information about immigrant stock is the data about numbers of residence permits issued to third-country nationals. This kind of statistical information is collected by the General Inspectorate for Immigration but is not available publicly in any national database. Eurostat, however, gathers this kind of data which allows analysis of the changing numbers of non-EU citizens residing in Romania.

Table 3. Total numbers of all valid residence permits at the end of each year, 2008-2019.
Source: Eurostat (2020a).

	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
Total	58 736	61 800	60 402	60 730	53 648	55 519	57 517	61 413	62 882	54 045	59 862	79 465

Figure 7. All valid residence permits by reasons on 31 December of each year, 2008-2019.
Source: Eurostat (2020a).

As depicted by Figure 7. above, the number of valid permits at the end of every year changed dynamically between 2008 and 2019. Especially numbers of valid permits issued due to family reasons and due to work have been fluctuating significantly. Considering the second category, in the period between 2008 and 2017, the numbers of permits were mostly decreasing but the tendency changed after 2017. The numbers of valid permits increased dynamically, from 3 551 at the end of 2017 to 20 655 at the end of 2019. Concerning reasons linked with education, and other reasons, there was an observable change in the trend. The numbers of valid permits issued on those grounds have been declining until the end of 2014 and after that, the numbers of valid permits have been mostly growing. Taking into consideration reasons such as refugee status and subsidiary protection, the number of permits issued on their basis has been slightly growing until the end of 2015 and since then there is a relatively stable number of immigrants holding permits granted on those grounds.

Figure 8. Numbers of Romanian citizenships acquired by foreigners, 1999-2018.
Source: Eurostat (2020b).

The number of citizenships granted to foreigners might also be an interesting information concerning immigration to Romania and integration of foreigners, at least at the formal level (Figure 8).

The data gathered in the Eurostat database is fragmented and numbers of people granted Romanian citizenship are only estimates concerning 2007 and the period of 2013-2018. For some years there is no available information, and for years 2017 and 2018 there is no disaggregated data that would indicate origin of immigrants, except for information whether they come from EU member states or not. Except for those difficulties, available data show that 39 953 foreigners acquired Romanian citizenships in the period of 1999-2018. 21 735 (54,4%) of them were Europeans, mostly from countries outside of the EU. The largest groups of immigrants granted Romanian citizenship in that period of time were the Moldovans (12 142) and Ukrainians (8276), for whom it might be easy due to their Romanian ethnicity (concerning Moldovans especially and some Ukrainians⁶). In many cases it might also be a way of obtaining European Union's citizenship in order to be able to migrate to wealthier West-European countries in the future (Anghel & Coşciug, 2018: 5). Moreover, 1601 foreigners coming from Asian countries were granted Romanian citizenship which amounted to 4% of all. There were people originating from Syria (400 persons), Iraq (353), Iran (273), Israel (224), Lebanon (216),

⁶ It is due to historical processes in the region, concerning especially today's borders' areas in Moldova and Ukraine where ethnic Romanians live. More on the topic: <https://doi.org/10.1080/14650040802693796> (accessed: 02.04.2021).

Jordan (139), Vietnam (69) and others. Another large group of foreigners who acquired Romanian citizenship between 1999-2018 were stateless persons - 2192 of them and ones with unknown citizenship - 682 (Eurostat, 2020b).

Immigrant stock has been constantly growing in Romania which can be proven by various kinds of statistical data. Some reasons for that might be that there have been policy incentives supposed to enable more intensive immigration and also respond to the shortages in Romanian labour market. e.g.: the 2018 Action Plan to implement the National Strategy on Immigration for 2015-18 which has added a couple of instruments aimed at simplifying procedures for some groups of immigrant workers, as well as facilitating social integration (OECD, 2020). Moreover, since 2018 new legal measures have been to facilitate immigration and simplify the procedures for residence and work permits. The minimum wage for immigrants, equal to that for Romanian citizens, is also guaranteed (OECD, 2020). Another policy regards encouragement of immigrants who are ethnic Romanians to take up studies in Romanian universities. As noted by Fleşer (2012: 73), a large share of foreign students come from the Republic of Moldova as a result of that incentive.

Picture: Razvan Cristea/Unsplash.com

5. Immigrant flows in Romania

Similarly to other migration processes taking place in Romania, assessing the true scale of inflows of immigrants is difficult due to several reasons. For instance, return migration of Romanian citizens, constituting a large part of yearly immigrant inflows have not been taken into consideration in the migration statistics held by national institutions (Anghel et al., 2018:4). Also, due to the fact that Romania is a member state of European Union and the Schengen zone, it is complicated to keep track of whole process.

Permanent immigration

Concerning immigrant flows, the National Institute of Statistics' database contains information about permanent and temporary immigrants solely. Permanent migrants, as it was discussed in the methodological section, are those who change their permanent residence address from one abroad to the other one in Romania. The statistics on the total international permanent immigration is available for the period of 1991-2019, however the information on specific countries of origin starts since 1994. Figure 9. below depicts changes in total numbers of permanent migrants registered yearly in Romania, compared with immigrants coming from Moldova, which is the main country of origin of all the immigrants settling in Romania yearly. In the periods of 1998-2002, 2005-2006 and 2011-2019 the share of Moldovan immigrants within the whole group of permanent immigrants coming to Romania exceeded 50% and amounted to a maximum value in 2001 and 2013 when it equalled around 84% and in 2000 when it amounted to 83%.

Other numerous groups of permanent immigrants settling in Romania yearly have been coming from such countries like Ukraine, Italy, Germany and the USA. Especially the number of immigrants originating from Ukraine increased significantly - from just 1157 persons in 2016 to 9040 in 2018. Importantly, there is a positive balance of permanent immigration to Romania since 2012, as observed by Valter-Alexandru Jianu (2020: 159). It was the first year since the beginning of the NIS' record of migration processes in Romania when immigration flow of permanent immigrants exceeded emigration flow.

Figure 9. Yearly inflows of permanent immigrants to Romania. Comparison of number of all the immigrants and immigrants coming from the Republic of Moldova, 1994- 2019.

Source: National Institute for Statistics (2020a).

Figure 10. The most numerous permanent immigrant groups by country of origin - yearly: 2002- 2019.
Source: National Institute for Statistics (2020a).

The sex structure of the yearly immigrant flows has been changing during the period of 1991-2019. In the first year of keeping track of migratory data, the feminization rate was the highest and amounted to 63,7%. In the following years the share of men in the group of permanent immigrants has always exceeded 50%:

Figure 11. Sex structure of the permanent immigrants inflows, 1991-2019.
Source: National Institute for Statistics (2020c).

In terms of the age structure of permanent immigrant inflows, some changes can also be observable. In 2008, a year after Romania's becoming a member state of European Union, the largest group of permanent migrants settling in the country were between 25 and 39 year old. In 2013, most foreigners coming to Romania as permanent immigrants were aged 20-34, with the prevalence of the group of people between 25 and 29 year old. Similar age structure was observed in 2019, when the group of immigrants aged 25-34 was the largest one. Most of the permanent immigrants settling in Romania are young adults in their productive age. A change that is observable between the age structure in 2008, 2013 and 2019 is the fact that the share of children and teenagers is larger than in previous years regarded.

Figure 12. Age structure of yearly inflows of permanent immigrants, 2008, 2013, 2019.
Source: National Institute for Statistics (2020c).

Long-term temporary immigration

Another kind of data collected by the NSI concerns long-term temporary immigrants - persons who changed their usual residence abroad with a usual place of residence in Romania. Long-term temporary immigrants are persons who reside or are expected to reside at the Romanian territory for at least 12 months. This data contains the return immigration and does not allow us to analyse the scale of immigration of foreigners only. It regards immigrants by their previous country of usual residence, therefore does not enable us to examine immigrant inflows from by country of origin or citizenship. The statistics on temporary immigration are available for the period of time starting in 2008, a year after the country's accession to the European Union.

The scale of temporary immigration is larger than that of the permanent one. While the number of long-term temporary immigrants reached 202 422 in 2019, it amounted only to 64 479 persons, concerning permanent immigration. Long-term temporary immigration is also characterized by a higher share of men than women in the migrant group, similarly to permanent immigration. The feminization rate has amounted to a maximum of 48% in 2014, which was the highest share of females in the yearly total temporary immigration to Romania in the period of 2008-2019.

Figure 13. Long-term temporary immigrants, 2008-2019.
Source: National Institute for Statistics (2020c).

The largest age group in the inflows of long-term temporary migrants has been changing comparing years 2008, 2013 and 2019. The age structure of the immigrant groups who arrived in Romania in all those years was characterized by the prevalence of young adults. In 2019 the largest group comprised of persons aged 25-34, similarly as in the permanent immigrant group in the same year. They were followed by immigrants between the age of 35 and 39, 20-24, and 40-44. In 2013, the largest age group also contained immigrants between 25 and 34 years old but with the dominance of people aged 25-29. Similar age structure can be observed in 2008 but there was also a relatively large number of immigrants aged 20-24. Interestingly, the number of persons in that age group was similar to the one in 2019 despite the fact that the total yearly numbers of long-term temporary immigrants arriving in Romania changed significantly. In general, the numbers of persons between 20-24 has been quite stable, oscillating around 20- 22 thousand, except for years 2013 and 2015-17 when it dropped slightly to the minimum of almost 15 thousand in 2015 (NIS, 2020c).

Figure 14. Comparison of the age structure of the long-term temporary immigrant group coming to Romania in 2008, 2013 and 2019.
Source: National Institute for Statistics (2020c).

Comparing the sex structure in the context of the age of immigrants, in 2019 women were dominating in terms of number in all the age groups older than 60 years. In 2013, there were more women in all the age groups above 50 years and in 2008, women were prevailing only in the age groups older than 70 years.

Table 4. Age structure of the long-term temporary immigrants coming to Romania in 2008, 2013 and 2019.

Source: National Institute for Statistics (2020c).

Age group	2008			2013			2019		
	Total	Male	Female	Total	Male	Female	Total	Male	Female
Total	138 929	85 421	53 508	153 646	84 790	68 856	202 422	117 643	84 779
0-4	3 871	1 979	1 892	6 128	3 166	2 962	6 286	3 415	2 871
5-9	3 447	1 798	1 649	7 043	3 639	3 404	6 573	3 357	3 216
10-14	2 358	1 201	1 157	5 031	2 609	2 422	5 410	2 753	2 657
15-19	5 736	3 089	2 647	5 801	3 056	2 745	9 829	5 278	4 551
20-24	21 504	12 209	9 295	16 782	8 913	7 869	22 544	13 547	8 997
25-29	22 456	13 826	8 630	26 184	15 587	10 597	31 124	18 127	12 997
30-34	22 019	14 318	7 701	23 810	14 265	9 545	36 383	21 308	15 075
35-39	19 031	12 722	6 309	15 851	8 813	7 038	22 969	14 330	8 639
40-44	13 956	9 254	4 702	14 727	8 771	5 956	20 945	13 508	7 437
45-49	9 187	6 033	3 154	10 532	5 876	4 656	13 883	8 520	5 363
50-54	7 337	4 684	2 653	8 460	4 164	4 296	10 298	5 789	4 509
55-59	4 223	2 518	1 705	6 622	3 049	3 573	6 837	3 483	3 354
60-64	1 668	880	788	3 787	1 699	2 088	4 835	2 241	2 594
65-69	957	480	477	1 639	701	938	2 593	1 193	1 400
70-74	524	192	332	722	297	425	1 055	453	602
75-79	332	151	181	346	121	225	456	190	266
80-84	191	52	139	149	51	98	267	105	162
85+	132	35	97	32	13	19	135	46	89

Figure 15. Long-term temporary immigrants by country of previous usual residence; the most numerous groups, 2013-2019.

Source: NIS (2021), personal communication via email.

The data available publicly does not specify the country of origin or country of previous residence of immigrants coming to Romania. However, National Institute of Statistics' officers shared information about the latter on our request. What is important to note in this context, the information on immigration based on the country of previous usual residence includes persons of all nationalities, including the Romanian one. Hence, it is hard to estimate the size of the inflow of foreigners solely because the statistics include return migrants as well.

As depicted by Figure 14. above, most of the long-term temporary immigrants coming to Romania during almost all the years from which there is available data, had their previous place of usual residence in Spain. Such a large scale of immigration from this country might indicate return or circular migration of Romanian citizens since Spain has been one of the main countries of emigration. Only in 2019 the group of immigrants coming from the Republic of Moldova was larger than the one of persons residing previously in Spain. Immigrants living previously in the Republic of Moldova have been the second largest group in the period of 2014-2018 and the numbers of immigrants coming from that country have been increasing significantly since 2017. Scale of immigration from Italy dropped by almost 55% between 2013 and 2014 (from 25 462 persons to 14 000). The numbers of persons coming to Romania from Germany have been quite stable in the period of 2013-2019 and oscillated between 12 700 immigrants in 2015 and 16 000 in 2017 and 2018. The fifth largest group of immigrants comes from the United Kingdom and have been growing steadily since 2013 with a drop in 2018. Significant increase in the number of immigrants residing previously in the UK between 2018 and 2019 might be a consequence of Brexit and probably indicates at intensified return migration of Romanian citizens.

Moreover, there has been a large increase in long-term temporary immigration from Asian countries in recent years. It might be a consequence of a growing labor demand since Romania keeps being an emigration country and both skilled and unskilled Romanian workers are leaving to other countries. As Vedran Obućina reports, the question of liberalizing Romanian labor market and opening it more widely to Asian immigrants becomes an urgent issue to policymakers (Obućina, 2019).

Table 5. Inflows of long-term temporary immigrants - most numerous groups coming from Asian countries, 2013-2019.

Source: NIS (2021), personal communication via email.

	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
Turkey	397	309	561	1 217	1 394	1 633	2 854
China	325	304	314	914	1 400	1 387	1 829
India	15	25	79	175	171	192	1 281
Sri Lanka	2	2	83	138	196	417	1 750
Nepal	0	3	4	51	138	400	1 589
Vietnam	25	19	14	117	687	1 680	3 335

Figure 16. Inflows of long-term temporary immigrants - the most numerous groups coming from Asian countries, 2013-2019.

Source: NIS (2021), personal communication via email.

Other data sources on immigrant flows

Another source of significant data about immigration flows is the information about residence permits and visas granted to third-country nationals in a particular year. Although it is not available in any national database, Eurostat gathers this kind of information in a yearly manner:

Table 6. First residence permits issued by sex and reason, 2010-2019.

Source: Eurostat (2021b).

TIME / REASON		TOTAL	FAMILY	EDUCATION	REMUNERATED ACTIVITIES	OTHER
2010	total	10 218	4 642	3 265	1 700	611
	female	4 698	2 640	1 493	340	225
2011	total	9 740	3 920	3 179	1 971	670
	female	4 212	2 110	1 341	543	218
2012	total	10 125	3 899	3 429	1 656	1 141
	female	4 224	2 077	1 395	372	380
2013	total	11 160	4 155	3 692	1 542	1 771
	female	4 600	2 139	1 460	328	673
2014	total	10 294	3 331	3 535	1 803	1 625
	female	3 973	1 700	1 304	368	601
2015	total	11 289	3 770	4 374	1 680	1 465
	female	4 637	1 955	1 724	435	523
2016	total	11 867	3 871	4 631	1 766	1 599
	female	5 203	2 123	1 978	445	657
2017	total	13 264	3 578	4 448	2 952	2 286
	female	5 327	1 930	1 932	584	881
2018	total	16 487	3 856	4 635	6 347	1 649
	female	5 733	2 167	2 119	765	682
2019	total	27 103	4 205	4 943	16 394	1 561
	female	7 228	2 479	2 227	1 890	632

Figure 17. First residence permits issued by sex and reason, 2010-2019.
Source: Eurostat (2021b).

As depicted by Figure 16. above, yearly numbers of residence permits granted to thirdcountry nationals due to reasons such as family, education and other premises have been changing throughout years but have not increased in such a dynamic way as the ones concerning work. Number of residence permits issued due to remunerated activities started to grow significantly in 2016 which is the main reason for the increase of the total numbers of permits. Residence permits have been issued mostly to men and the discrepancy between the number of documents granted to females and males is especially conspicuous concerning reasons linked to work (Table 6.). The increase of the numbers of residence permits issued due to remunerated activities has been observed recently due to the inflow of citizens of Asian countries mostly, such as Vietnam, Sri Lanka, Turkey, Nepal and others (Figure 17.). The total number of those permits granted yearly has been fluctuating substantially in the period of 2008-2019. A large drop in numbers, from more than 9 thousand to 1,7 thousand, was observed between the years 2008-2010 and in the period between 2010-2016 there was some kind of stagnation noticed - total yearly numbers of this kind of permits have not surpassed 2 thousand:

Table 7. First permits issued for remunerated activities by citizenship, 2008- 2019.
Source: Eurostat (2021c).

	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
Total	9 039	4 724	1 700	1 971	1 656	1 542	1 803	1 680	1 766	2 952	6 347	16 394

Concerning short-term (3-5 months and 6-11 months of validity) and long-term (12 months or more) residence permits issued on premises linked with remunerated activities, there were large differences in terms of numbers of types of documents issued in 2019. There were only 82 3-5 months long permits granted, mostly to the Ukrainians (27% of all the documents). In terms of residence permits valid 6-11 months, Romanian authorities granted 1 998 of them to third-country citizens, mostly to the Vietnamese (39% of all). Residence permits valid 12 months or longer were also granted to the Vietnamese mostly. Out of 14 314 of all those documents, 3 017 were issued to citizens of Vietnam (21% of all). Other numerous groups of foreigners who were granted this type of a residence permit consisted of foreigners with citizenship of Sri Lanka, Turkey, Nepal, Republic of Moldova, India and China. In general, 16 394 residence permits were issued in 2019 due to a reason linked with work, and 87% of them concerned a stay longer than 1 year (Eurostat, 2021c).

Figure 18. First permits issued for remunerated activities by citizenship, most numerous groups, 2008- 2019. Source: Eurostat (2021c).

Even though the General Inspectorate for Immigration does not publish any holistic data concerning residence and work permits, its evaluation of work in 2019 has been shared and presented some information about the number of documents issued, which sheds some additional light at immigration processes in Romania.

As stated on the IGI website, in 2019 the immigration police managed the stay of over 137 500 persons, out of which 84 228 were third-country nationals coming mostly from the Republic of Moldova, Turkey and China. Main grounds on which permits were granted to foreigners in 2019 were employment, family reasons (the right to family unity), studies, scientific research and permanent establishment of residence in Romania. There were also 15 470 visa applications submitted by foreigners from 56 countries and 11 241 of them were approved. Long-stay visas (8343) were issued mostly to citizens of the Republic of Moldova, Turkey, Israel and China and short-stay ones (2898) were approved for foreigners coming mostly from Lebanon, Iraq, Jordan and India (General Inspectorate for Immigration, 2020).

Concerning granting of work permits in 2019, there were over 33 600 registered applications and 29 800 of them were issued mostly to foreigners coming from Asia. There were 6282 work permits granted to the Vietnamese, 4324 to the Nepalese, 4100 to the Indians, 3448 to the Turkish, 3309 to the Moldovans and 3156 to the citizens of Sri Lanka. General Inspectorate for Immigration tracks also undocumented work and residence of foreigners. Concerning the first one, there were 546 immigrants working without legal documents detected in the companies controlled. In terms of illegal residence, there were 3155 foreigners detected who were residing in Romania without proper permits which displays an increase by 16% compared to the previous year (General Inspectorate for Immigration, 2020).

IGI also gives numbers of the asylum seekers but more detailed information can be found in the report of the Asylum Information Database (Nica, 2020). The report is based on the information submitted by the Directorate for Asylum and Integration of the General Inspectorate for Immigration. According to AIDA's publication, there were 2587 first-time applicants for the protection status in 2019. Most of them came from countries such as Iraq (686), Syria (460), Afghanistan (200), Algeria (130), Iran (127), Somalia (120), Bangladesh (112), Turkey (102), Morocco (81) and Tunisia (53). 287 of all the asylum seekers were granted refugee status and 276 of them were granted subsidiary protection. 722 applications were still processed at the end of 2020. The rate of applications accepted or rejected differs significantly depending on the country of origin of the asylum seeker. The most numerous group of persons seeking protection in Romania, the Iraqi, were granted refugee status only at a rate of 7,1% and 9% concerning the subsidiary protection. The rejection rate of applications amounted to 32% in 2019. The second largest group of asylum seekers, the Syrians, were granted refugee status at a much higher rate - 45,5% and the subsidiary protection at the level of 53,4%. The highest rejection rate of applications was observed in regard to the ones submitted by the Iranians - 49,4% of them were rejected in 2019. Most of the asylum seekers were men - 78,8% of all, and unaccompanied children constituted a group of 189 persons which was 7,3% of the whole group (Nica, 2020: 7-8).

The General Inspectorate for Immigration mentions also numbers of immigrants following the integration program in 2019. In total, there were 793 people enrolled, 349 from Syria, 136 from Iraq and 51 from Afghanistan (General Inspectorate for Immigration, 2020).

Abel and Cohen's estimates - comparison with the local data

One of the aims of the report is also to compare the national statistics with the estimations of bilateral international migration flows by Abel and Cohen (2019). The latest dataset analyzed by the authors came from the United Nations Population Division (UNCPD) and covers the 5-year period between 2011 and 2015. According to their estimates, around 46 266 people immigrated to Romania. The most numerous groups of migrants came from the Republic of Moldova (14 510), Bulgaria (5843), Ukraine (4035), Italy (3762), Russia (2339). Comparing our calculations based on immigrant stock data from Census 2011 (NIS, 2011) and the same type of information derived from Eurostat database concerning 2015, it seems that Abel and Cohen's estimates in the Romanian case are largely understated.

Table 8. Immigrant (net) flow between 2015 and 2011. Calculations based on immigrant stock data from local sources compared to Abel and Cohen's estimates.

Source: NSI (2011), Eurostat (2021a), Abel & Cohen (2019).

	Census 2011	Eurostat 2015	Immigrant flow	Abel and Cohen's estimates
Total	133 368	281 048	147 680	46 266
Republic of Moldova	28 603	114 654	86 051	14 510
Bulgaria	9 309	10 465	1 156	5 843
Ukraine	6 685	11 900	5 215	4 035
Italy	17 510	38 580	21 070	3 762
Russian Federation	3 643	5 269	1 626	2 339

For instance, total immigrant flow between 2015 and 2011 computed by Abel and Cohen is more than 3 times smaller than the one computed by us, based on the local data. Even larger discrepancies are observable concerning groups of Moldovans and Italians - the inflow of those immigrants seem to be more than 5 times larger in reality than in Abel and Cohen's dataset. Immigrant flow of Ukrainians was also underestimated by them but not so dramatically as in the previous cases - it seems to be 1,3 times larger based on local data. Moreover, concerning Bulgarian and Russian immigrants, calculations of the authors were most likely wrong - according to the information we have gathered in this report, the population of foreigners coming from those countries has been shrinking. It is therefore impossible that they were among the most numerous groups of migrants arriving in Romania in the regarded period of time. Taking into consideration large discrepancies between calculations made by us and the data provided by Abel and Cohen, it seems that their estimates are not reliable for analysing immigration in Romania. What is more, immigration processes have essentially changed in this country in the period after 2015. Not only have yearly inflows of immigrants been increasing significantly but also - there have been more foreigners coming from other countries than before - the Asian ones, for instance. As a consequence, Abel and Cohen's estimates cannot be used as a tool for prognosing future migration processes in Romania.

Picture: Alex Blajan/Unsplash.com

6.Scenario narratives for Romania

This chapter focuses on the existing migration potential of Romania as a sending and host country, taking into account the analysis of important push and pull factors from such dimensions as demographic structure, economy, technology, social attitudes, governance indicators. As such, these scenario narratives do not aim to foresee the migration future of Romania but rather to outline the possible future directions in which demographic processes can develop, including international migration.

Analysis of Romania migration potential

In this section of the chapter, we focus on the migration potential of the Romanian country, taking into account six dimensions, namely: demography, economy, technology and technological development, society, governance and environment. The introduced aspects are crucial while building a narrative scenario.

Demography

Starting with demographic potential, Romania is a country with a low fertility rate which in 2019 amounted to 1,77. However, it needs to be pointed out that the score is positively changing for the Romanian society as over the years the fertility rate is constantly growing. For instance, in 2011 the indicator was 1,47 and in 2018 - 1,76 (Eurostat, 2021d).

However, the life expectancy at birth slightly increases - between 1990 and 2018 it lengthened by 5,4 years, of which 5 years by males and 6,1 by females (Eurostat, 2020). Romanians are a rapidly ageing population with an overrepresentation of older women living in rural areas. As it has been assumed by Bodogai and Cutler, the senior Romanians are expected to represent more than 30 per cent of the total population by 2050 (Bodogai & Cutler, 2013: 147-148). In turn, according to the assumptions published by the National Institute of Statistics (NIS), the Romanian population will gradually decline and by 2050 will reach a figure of 15 million persons, in other words - an annual decrease of nearly 130 thousand individuals. Consequently, it is assumed that in thirty years the Romanian society will be declined with the overrepresentation of the elderly (NIS, 2020). This gap can be filled by the immigration flow as not to lead to dramatic shortages in the labour force.

The influx of migrants is underestimated and so far there is no continuing tendency regarding immigration and emigration flows as their number is constantly changing.

However, we can indicate a trend that emigration figures overweight immigration figures. For instance, in 2019 the number of events of immigration was the highest in general, namely 202 thousand yet the number of emigration events was even higher - 233 thousand persons (Eurostat, 2020).

Economy

Although Romania is a country with one of the higher poverty rates in the European Union, the risk of poverty and social exclusion has significantly decreased from 43 per cent in 2012 to 37 per cent in 2015. At the same time, the share of Romanians was at risk of poverty after social transfers increased from 23 per cent in 2012 to 25 per cent in 2015 (World Bank, 2021a). Fortunately, the economy of Romania is greatly changing as the government tends to raise the development and investment indicators. Due to implemented economic reforms, the Romanian financial sector is experiencing growth. In 2019 the per capita income was 12,630\$ which classified Romania as a high-income country for the first time (World Bank, 2021b). Also, the

unemployment rate is spectacularly decreasing. Before the Covid-19 pandemic, the period from 2010 to 2019 has characterised by a decline of 4 per cent, namely 7% in 2010 and 2,9% in 2019 (Eurostat, 2021g).

Despite the decreasing unemployment rate, the Romanian economy still experiences shortages in the labour market. To deal with the problem policymakers aim to liberalise the job market and widely open it to immigrants from Asian countries. The most numerous migrant groups residing in Romania are Vietnamese, Turkish, Chinese, Sri Lankan, Nepali and Indian (read more on page 39). Besides, the Romanian government has announced the National Strategy on Immigration. The main goal of the implementation of the document was to attract immigrants with Romanian background (read more on page 27).

The shortage in the Romanian labour market will significantly impact the agricultural sector and industry of logging and manufacturing. In agriculture around 20 per cent of Romania's active population is employed and represents around 4 per cent of the country's GDP. In turn, the manufacturing sector contributes 17 per cent of annual GDP and it is assumed that this number will grow. The industry of logging is developing very fast as one-quarter of Romania is covered by forest. Moreover, a large share of the Romanian industry sector are heavy industry, manufacturing of vehicle parts, building and construction (Santander Analysis, 2021). Nonetheless, because of the automatization and digitalisation, the sectors of industry and agriculture will slowly employ fewer and fewer persons in favour of machines which is going to affect the status of the foreign workforce.

Governance

One of the prominent aspects in the migration narrative scenario is governance (de Jong & Boissonneault, 2020: 11). In this section of the chapter, we will focus on the role of the Romanian government within migration flows.

In contrast to other post-Soviet Bloc countries, Romania's transition in 1989 has been accompanied by the revolution that resulted in the overthrow and execution of the communist leader Nicolae Ceaușescu (Bodogai & Cutler, 2013: 148). Nowadays Romania is governed by the Social Democratic Party (SDP) established by the former president Ion Iliescu. Although the SDP is a centrist-left in economic domains, its social policy is rather conservative which manifests in referring to religion and traditional family structure. The minority government is being ruled by the National Liberal Party (NLP). The head of state is associated with NLP president Klaus Iohannis who in 2019 successfully won the elections and therefore held the office for the second time (Pieńkowski, 2020).

New authorities will mainly focus on mitigating pandemic consequences by refining the healthcare system and restoration of the national economy (Cațus, 2020). The changes would positively impact potential immigration flows and enhance the attractiveness of Romania. However, no migration policy may cause the odds in the adaptation process of potential immigrants.

Society

While analysing the potential of migration inflows we need to consider the ethnic, national, and religious minorities in each country. The domestic cohesion and capacity for migrant integration are crucial for social development. Therefore, the status of minorities and attitudes toward immigrants provide insight into necessary societal factors (de Jong & Boissonneault, 2020: 11). We aim to assess the degree of integration capacity of the potential immigrants in Romania.

Romanian society has a rather negative attitude toward immigrants and refugees. As it has been proven in several studies and polls [1], the major share of Romanians perceives receiving refugees with prejudice. According to the poll conducted in 2016 by INS, ca. 85 per cent of respondents declared that they "do not want migrants and refugees in Romania". (British Council & Romanian National Council for Refugees, 2018: 5-8). It needs to be, however, pointed out that antiimmigrant sentiments have been reinforced after the financial

crisis in 2011. Yet during the migration crisis in 2015 traditional Romanian media have been relatively neutral with slightly negative rhetoric against refugees from the Middle East and Africa (Erbel et al., 2019: 19-20).

Due to communist past that emphasised the homogenous nature of a national state, the autochthonous minorities in Romania may still face social exclusion. The largest minority of Hungarians (also called Szeklers), which in 2011 constituted to 6,1 per cent of the overall population (Minority Rights Group, 2020), endeavours for recognition of Hungarian as the official language. It is reported that the Hungarian minority has stymied access to higher education and the labour market (Vehrer, Belényesi & Reddin, 2017: 50-54). On the other hand, it is important to stress that the Hungarian minority also enjoys some privileges, such as a political representation (the Democratic Union of Hungarians in Romania), TV programs in Hungarian language, etc.

In the disadvantage is also the Romani community which in 2011 equated to 3 per cent of the overall population (Minority Rights Group, 2020). The group struggles with lacks in access to the job market and equal payments, health care, and house utilities like electricity and water (European Commission, 2014: 101-104).

Unprivileged position of the two largest minorities in Romania on par with prevailing hostility towards immigrants among the overall society, may be a serious obstacle in the migrants' integration process in Romania.

Environment

Although environmental factors are not favoured by many researchers, they are crucial while assessing migration movements especially in the case of long-term prognosis. Therefore, mean annual temperature and precipitation data and risk of air pollution, droughts, floods and sudden storms should be considered. Analysis of those factors are major while building narrative scenario.

Starting with temperature rises by days and nights, it is assumed that the number of hot days in Romania will increase by 13 days in the period of 2040-2059. It is expected that the number of tropical nights - with a temperature of min. 20°C - will also rise (World Bank, 2020). What is more, Romania is at risk of decreasing snowfalls and rainfalls which would cause droughts. Periods with no precipitation would highly affect the agriculture-based economy of the country. Socio-economic changes are also inevitable as the southern and eastern parts of Romania are expected to be at hardest hit by increased temperature (World Bank, 2020).

Furthermore, Romania is at risk of the earthquake and the capital city is the most prone to be exposed to damages. As the Romanian government does not endeavour to prevent the hazard, some groups of activists and decision-makers try to raise awareness about the expected earthquake (Simpson, Pomonis & Georgescu, 2020).

In conclusion, we assess that in the upcoming decades Romania will be likely to produce small-scale emigration flows. Due to aforementioned temperature increase, risk of massive snowfalls, storms, droughts and possible earthquake Romania may be the origin country of environmental migrants. As twenty per cent of Romanian working age population is currently employed in the agriculture (see: Economy section), environmental factors will negatively impact this sector and even cause its malfunction which may lead to famine and instability. Hence, many workers, including foreign labour force, are likely to become climate refugees.

Country-specific:

In this section we will characterise the main migration networks in Romania. This step is necessary to assess if a given network will increase or diminish in the future. The assumption base on official data included in this report. In section 7.2.1 we take into account the size of the group, its development, the most important features and the situation in the country of origin.

Existing migration networks

Romania is a country with a growing immigrant population. In 2019 the foreign population accounted for at least 3 per cent of the overall society. Due to mentioned in section 3 underestimation of the migrant groups in the local data and discrepancy stemming from the specific way of registering immigrants, not by their nationality but place of the previous residence, we cannot clearly define the migration networks in Romania. We can observe the correlation between the events of emigration and re-emigration to assess the actual number of immigrants. As has been presented in Figure 1 and Figure 2, Romanians emigrated mostly to United Kingdom, Italy, Germany, Spain, Austria, Belgium, Denmark and France.

Therefore, we can assume that influx of groups from Italy, Spain and Germany are in fact return migrants (see: Figure 5). Therefore, we would like to focus on the inflow of Moldovans, Hungarians, Bulgarians and Ukrainians, but also growing communities of Vietnamese, Turkish, Chinese, Sri Lankans, Nepalis and Indians. It needs to be pointed out that the first four mentioned nationalities have migrated to Romania after opening its borders in the 1990s.

Starting with the major network of Moldovans it needs to be pointed out that in 2019 the population of Moldovans reached 250 thousand. Hence, we can indicate the growth of the community (Eurostat, 2021a). Another important feature is the feminisation rate – according to 2011 Census results, women represented over sixty per cent of the community. It will significantly impact the fertility of the migrant network. The group is prone to grow in the following years not only because of the fertility rate but also due to the cultural and language proximity of the Romanian and Moldovan nations. Another very significant factor in assessing Moldovans' immigration potential is pro-Romanian sentiments. As recent studies show, due to unstable government and so-called unirea, namely the idea of uniting Moldova with Romania proposed by Moldovans (Cațus, 2021) the number of Moldovan citizens in Romania will likely increase.

The second-largest group residing in Romania are Ukrainians. The community in 2019 accounted for nearly 40 thousand persons. In the period of the recent five years the number of immigrants from Ukraine has significantly increased as in 2014 the figure remained 10 thousand persons (Eurostat, 2021a). As the economic situation in Ukraine is being more stable and the influx of Ukrainians to Romania after its peak in 2016 slowly declines (NIS, 2020a) it is assumed the decreasing tendency will remain.

The community of **Bulgarians** is present in Romania since the 1990s. The number of Bulgarians since 2013 remains at slightly the same level which is around 10 thousand persons (Eurostat, 2021a). Roman Catholics live near the border with Serbia whilst Eastern Orthodox Bulgarians reside in the southern parts of Romania (Minority Rights Group, 2020). Two geographical centres of residence and division concerning religious affiliation impact the inner structure of the immigrant network and impede its potential bonds.

Apart from Szekler Hungarian minority, a small group of Hungarian citizens inflows Romania. The number of Hungarian immigrants is slightly increasing and the figures in 2019 remained less than 10 thousand persons (Eurostat, 2021a). Because of the aspirations of the Szeklers and the emigration nature of Hungary, it is supposed that the community will slowly grow.

We should take a deeper glance at the Asian originated population flows as the figures show the increase regarding migrants granted a long-term temporary stay. In the period between 2013 and 2019, the data presents the outstanding growth of all mentioned groups: Vietnamese, Turkish, Chinese, Sri Lankans, Nepalis and Indians (NIS, 2021). All of them are located in big cities, especially in Bucharest. All of those groups are expected to grow but at a different pace.

The largest community with Asian background is **Vietnamese** which in 2019 accounted for over 3 thousand persons. It needs to be noticed that in 2015 the official statistics showed no immigrants from Viet Nam (NIS, 2021). This increase may stem from the start of permitting by the office the foreigners to stay but also building a strong migrant network.

Turkish citizens are another rapidly growing group - between 2013 and 2019 their number increased sixfold (NIS, 2021). In 2013 Turkish citizens were the largest groups with an Asian background, so taking into account their long presence in the Romanian labour market, historical bonds, higher fertility rate of the group than the Romanian nationals, and the hostile political atmosphere in Turkey it is assumed that the number of Turkish immigrants in Romania will sharply increase.

Another two immigrant communities in Romania are **Chinese** and **Sri Lankan** citizens whose both numbers in 2019 oscillated around 1800 persons. As there is no accurate data on those new groups there is no tool to assess their future in Romania. However, basing on the sharp difference in the number of Sri Lankans in 2018 (417) and 2019 (1750), it is expected for them to grow more intensively in comparison to the Chinese population (NIS, 2021).

Nepali and **Indian** communities are also characterised by a quick tempo of growth. For instance, in 2018 the number of Nepalis equated to 400 and in 2019 nearly 1600. In turn, the number of Indians in 2018 totalled to 192, and in 2019 – 1300 (See: Table 5). The Indian minority is expected to increase rapidly in the following years bearing in mind India's demographic potential. When it comes to Nepalis, it is presumed that the increase will remain in the following years yet will stop in a long-term distance as the largest Nepali diasporas in the EU are located in Germany, France, Spain and Portugal (The Official Portal of Government of Nepal). Also, future of those new networks will be determined by the economic recovery of the state after Covid-19 pandemic.

Re-emigration

Return migration is a vast source of population inflow. As it has been mentioned in the report, even half of all households with migrant family-member have a returnee. The scale of return migration is not precisely estimated as the official data base on self-reporting of migrants. Therefore, we can suppose that the temporary stayers are much more underestimated than permanent ones.

It is concluded that inflows of the population from the United Kingdom, Italy, Spain, Germany, USA and France are in fact return migration events. This surmise can be proven by the data consisting of age and country of birth of the immigrants. As it has been mentioned in section 4, 40 per cent of the immigrant stock were persons under the age of 15. What is more, most of these persons were born in the European Union countries, particularly in the United Kingdom. The high share of children and teenagers born outside Romania is at risk of insufficient integration to the Romanian society, if the authorities will not provide adequate policies facilitating this process.

Recruitment agencies

The role of the recruitment agencies should be considered whilst building narrative scenario. However, the institutions located in Romania mostly enhance the emigration trend among the natives. The agencies send employees to countries of the Schengen area.

Asylum-seekers and refugees

Another important point to discuss is receiving refugees due to military conflicts, political violence and climate change. Romanian state does not receive refugees on a large scale. In 2019 the rejection rate of application has equated to 32 per cent. Most asylum seekers originated from the MENA region, peculiarly from Iraq and Syria (Nica, 2020: 7-8). However, the refugee status is not the only option for asylum seekers. Following EU law, an asylum-seeker in Romania can be granted subsidiary protection.

Pandemic

The Covid-19 pandemic has sharply impacted the rapidly developing economy of Romania. In 2019 the overall economic structure has decreased by 3,9 per cent. Due to infections and national and partial lockdowns the industrial sector has suffered the most as has contracted by 9,3 per cent. On par with the industry, trade and services have also been heavily affected by the pandemic and the sector decreased by 4,7 per cent in 2020. In the disadvantage is agriculture, employing around 20 per cent of the whole population, that has been hit not only by the pandemic, but also droughts. In consequence, the unemployment rate has risen and accounted for 5,3 in December 2020. What is more, due to Covid-19 outbreak it is expected that the poverty rate will also rise (World Bank, 2021b).

The recovery depends on the success of the vaccination programme and economic reforms implemented. After the impairment of trade, transport and tourism industries, it is presumed that the GDP will grow by 2 per cent in 2021 and 4,4 per cent in 2022 (OECD, 2020).

Picture: Catalin Paterau/Unsplash.com

7. Concluding remarks

This report has presented an outline of immigration trends in Romania.

The wide consensus that existing official statistics on migration do not adequately depict complex realities and lead to various misestimations (e.g. Massey, 2010) has also been observed in the case of Romania. Available statistical data sets cover only a part of the actual migration flows and stocks. The social construction of categories applied in grasping migration dynamics make it much harder to analyse than e.g., other components of population growth, i.e., fertility or mortality. International migration processes additionally are connected closely with the issues such as national identity, ideologies, citizenship, entitlement, national interests which have an impact on migration-related definitions, classifications and the methodology (Ibidem).

There are numerous problems with both availability and reliability of the official statistical data on migration stocks and flows in Romania (c.f. Andrn et al., 2016; Otoi, Titan, E., 2015). There are many factors behind the biases in statistics, e.g., the changeable nature of many forms of migration (in particular the seasonal one), undeclared character of many migration movements, the methodology of collecting migration data on the basis of self-reporting, or the phenomenon of illegal migration. Therefore, due to an incomplete coverage, the migration flows are significantly underestimated for Romania.

According to the existing official data, however, increasing immigration can be observed in Romania, especially in recent years, concerning both temporary and permanent immigration. The Romanian immigration potential is growing due to the economic growth (impeded by the Covid-19 pandemic) and demographic shortages of the national population. Not only the immigrant population has been growing, but also its structure has been changing. There is an increasing masculinization of the immigrant group residing in Romania and the share of the youngest immigrants is also growing. The Republic of Moldova keeps being the main country of origin of immigrants deciding to migrate to Romania, followed by Italy, Spain, Germany and the United Kingdom. In aforementioned cases, it is, however, very likely that a high share of persons coming from the EU member states are Romanian return migrants, but it is impossible to estimate the scale of that process based on the public data. It needs, however, to be pointed out that policymakers should implement proper policies addressed to returning migrants' children to successfully adapt them to parents' homeland, especially if the influx will remain. Moreover, immigrants have been recently arriving from "non-traditional" countries, too. A significant increase in numbers of persons originating from South-Eastern Asian states such as Vietnam, Nepal, Sri Lanka, India, etc. is quite a new phenomenon in Romania. According to the data presented in this report, these are mostly labour migrants, therefore their presence in the Romanian labour market might become more influential in the future.

Romania is changing from being solely an emigration country. As underlined by Anghel and Cociug, its migration landscape is starting to be characterised not only by emigration of Romanian citizens but also by transit migration and intensifying immigration of increasingly diverse groups of foreigners (Anghel & Cociug, 2018: 4). In such a perspective, it is essential for Romanian authorities to gather more nuanced and unified statistical information about immigrants coming to their country in order to be able to create specific migration policies in the future. Moreover, more kinds of information should be available publicly because the data available currently at the NIS database is fragmented and does not present the full picture of the migration landscape in Romania and of characteristics of the immigrant population already residing in this country.

The pandemic of Covid-19 which started in February 2019 had a deep impact on the socio-economic situation in Romania. The population decline has been reinforced due to Coronavirus infections which was particularly harmful in the ageing society. In the context of migration movements, the pandemic strongly impeded the phenomenon and disrupted short-term mobility due to closing borders.

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